
Project INNOHYPPY: Innovative catalyst and its regeneration for clean hydrogen production via methane pyrolysis

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Report on catalyst regeneration

Intro

This report presents the investigation of catalyst regeneration methods for catalysts deactivated during methane pyrolysis for hydrogen production. The work focused on the application of non-thermal plasma (NTP) treatment as a cleaner alternative to conventional catalyst regeneration techniques. The regeneration approach aimed to remove carbonaceous deposits formed on Fe-based catalysts during methane pyrolysis and to restore catalytic activity.

Methane pyrolysis is considered a promising low-carbon hydrogen production pathway because it produces hydrogen and solid carbon without direct CO₂ formation during the main reaction. However, catalyst deactivation remains one of the main technological challenges limiting the long-term operation of methane pyrolysis systems.

Catalyst deactivation occurs mainly due to coke deposition and sintering of active catalytic sites. Carbon accumulation blocks active sites and eventually leads to reduced methane conversion and lower hydrogen production rates. Conventional catalyst regeneration methods include air combustion, steam gasification, and CO₂-assisted regeneration. Although effective in some applications, these approaches may suffer from disadvantages such as CO₂ generation, catalyst degradation, high energy demand, or process complexity.

Non-thermal plasma treatment has attracted increasing interest as a potential low-temperature regeneration approach capable of selectively removing carbonaceous deposits while preserving catalyst structure. In this work, non-thermal plasma treatment was investigated as a regeneration concept for Fe-based catalysts used in methane pyrolysis.

Methodology

The catalyst regeneration experiments were performed using a modified plasma treatment setup based on a magnetron physical vapor deposition chamber (PVD 75). It is worth to mention that before the experiments with PDV 75, the old plasma vacuum chamber with the possibility to initiate plasma treatment process was tested. However, process was unstable due to complexity to have a stable gas mixture flow to the chamber. Therefore, after few weeks of experiments by trying to stabilize the process, it was decided to move the plasma treatment to PVD 75 system, having much more stable gas flow (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Old vacuum chamber for magnetron sputtering and plasma treatment (left), and PVD 75 system for magnetron sputtering and plasma treatment (right)

The coked catalyst obtained after methane pyrolysis was subjected to non-thermal plasma treatment under different gas atmospheres. The plasma treatment system incorporated an auxiliary magnet positioned beneath the catalyst holder to direct plasma flux toward the catalyst surface and improve plasma interaction with the coked catalyst.

Table 1. Plasma treatment conditions

Parameter	Value
Pressure	9×10^{-2} mbar
Power	400 W
Voltage	700 V
Treatment time	30 min, 60 min, 180 min
Gas	Pure hydrogen Hydrogen/argon mixtures Hydrogen/oxygen mixtures
Modification	1 st approach: coked catalyst positioned on the Fe plate 2 nd approach: coked catalyst positioned beneath the Fe plate on a ceramic crucible 3 rd approach: coked catalyst positioned beneath the Fe plate on a ceramic crucible containing a magnetic rod

Main equipment to evaluate carbon removal is X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), because it is a highly surface-sensitive analytical technique capable of determining the elemental composition and chemical states of the outermost nanometers of the catalyst surface, making it particularly suitable for monitoring surface carbon concentration changes and evaluating plasma-induced catalyst surface modifications after regeneration treatment.

Results

Non-thermal plasma (NTP) treatment experiments were performed using an Fe target, where glow-discharge plasma was generated in atmospheres of pure H₂ as well as H₂/Ar and H₂/O₂ gas mixtures. Three different NTP treatment configurations were investigated in order to enhance carbon removal from the surface of the coked catalyst.

In the first configuration (Figure 2a), a glass Petri dish containing the coked catalyst was positioned directly on the Fe plate. The influence of several plasma-treatment parameters, including gas composition, plasma power, operating pressure, and treatment duration, was systematically evaluated. Despite these variations, only a minor degree of carbon removal, amounting to a few percent of the surface carbon, was achieved.

In the second configuration (Figure 2b), the glass Petri dish was placed beneath the Fe plate on a ceramic crucible rather than directly on the plate surface. This arrangement resulted in a slight improvement in carbon-removal efficiency; however, the overall removal rate remained limited.

The relatively low carbon-removal efficiency observed in both configurations was attributed to the insufficient concentration of reactive plasma species and their weak interaction with the coked catalyst surface. Consequently, a third configuration was developed to intentionally direct the plasma flux toward the catalyst surface. In this approach (Figure 2c), the glass Petri dish was positioned beneath the Fe plate on a ceramic crucible containing a magnetic rod, thereby enhancing the interaction between the generated plasma and the catalyst surface.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the investigated plasma-treatment configurations employing an Fe plate for glow-discharge plasma generation and a glass Petri dish containing the coked catalyst: (a) the Petri dish positioned directly on the Fe plate; (b) the Petri dish positioned beneath the Fe plate on a ceramic crucible; and (c) the Petri dish positioned beneath the Fe plate on a ceramic crucible containing a magnetic rod.

Table 2. Concentration of plasma treated coked catalyst

Sample				Elemental concentration, at. %				Surface carbon removal, %
				C	O	Al	Fe	
				C	O	Al	Fe	-
Coked catalyst				77.4	15.4	7.2	-	-
Type of plasma treatment modification	Gas composition via treatment, %			-	-	-	-	-
	H ₂	Ar	O ₂	-	-	-	-	-
1 st	100	-	-	77.3	16.7	7.0	-	-
1 st	80	20	-	74.4	15.2	7.5	2.9	
1 st	80	-	20	74.5	15.8	7.2	2.5	
2 nd	100	-	-	77.6	15.1	7.1	0.2	
2 nd	80	20	-	68.0	21.8	7.6	2.6	
2 nd	80	-	20	68.9	21.1	8.1	1.9	
3 rd	100	-	-	76.2	16.5	6.7	0.6	1.5
3 rd	97	3	-	71.4	18.9	8.7	1.0	7.8
3 rd	95	5	-	64.1	24.3	9.6	2.0	17.1
3 rd	90	10	-	56.3	31.3	6.3	6.1	27.3
3 rd	80	20	-	51.7	35.2	5.5	7.6	33.2
3 rd	97	-	3	67.7	22.3	8.2	1.8	12.5
3 rd	95	-	5	49.8	35.3	11.3	3.6	35.6
3 rd	90	-	10	49.6	35.6	11.0	3.8	35.9
3 rd	80	-	20	47.5	37.7	8.0	6.8	38.6

Surface carbon removal was calculated according to the following equation:

$$R = \frac{(C_{in} - C_{tr})}{C_{in}} \times 100 \%$$

Where R means Surface carbon removal in %, C_{in} – carbon concentration of initial (coked catalyst), C_{tr} – carbon concentration of plasma treated catalyst.

Conclusions

- This work investigated the application of non-thermal plasma treatment for regeneration of coked catalysts used in methane pyrolysis for hydrogen production. Plasma-assisted regeneration enabled partial removal of surface carbon deposits while preserving the structural integrity of the catalyst.
- The most effective plasma treatment conditions involved hydrogen–oxygen plasma mixtures combined with magnet-assisted plasma focusing. Under these conditions, approximately 38% surface carbon removal was achieved.
- Despite successful partial decoking, the regenerated catalyst exhibited limited recovery of methane pyrolysis performance (results of methane pyrolysis are not included into this report). The results therefore demonstrate that plasma-assisted regeneration is a promising proof-of-concept approach but requires further optimization before practical implementation.

- Future research should focus on improving plasma–surface interaction, optimizing gas composition and plasma parameters, reducing catalyst oxidation effects, and increasing catalytic activity recovery.

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